

- ASAE SCIENTIFIC COUNCIL -

- Opinion nº004/2020

SUBJECT: CAN CORONAVIRUS BE TRANSMITTED THROUGH FOOD?

REQUESTED BY: ASAE

RESUMO: Em resposta à questão: “O Coronavírus pode ser transmitido através da comida?” o Conselho Científico da ASAE verificou que todos os trabalhos de investigação até agora realizados mostram que não existe evidência que o SARS-COV-2 constitua um risco de segurança alimentar, não se considerando esse vírus de origem alimentar. Assim, o risco de contrair COVID-19 através de comida contaminada ou através de embalagens de comida é classificado como muito baixo. Até ao momento não existem casos de transmissão pela comida ou por embalagens da mesma. O vírus é primariamente um vírus respiratório que poderá também entrar na corrente sanguínea através das mucosas dos olhos. A existência de vírus em superfícies diversas, nomeadamente em embalagens de alimentos, e a sua persistência é conhecida pelo que se recomenda seguir as normas de higiene adequadas, e que começam invariavelmente com a lavagem das mãos previamente ao manuseio de alimentos. Esses cuidados devem ser reforçados a nível profissional devido ao alto número de embalagens manuseadas e alimentos processados.

O Conselho Científico da ASAE considera que, perante as evidências existentes, é seguro consumir alimentos, incluindo frutas e vegetais, valorizando-se as boas práticas de higienização normal das áreas de preparação de alimentos e dos alimentos frescos como na fase não pandémica.

ABSTRACT: In response to the question: "Can Coronavirus be transmitted through food?" the ASAE Scientific Council has verified that all research work carried out so far shows that there is no evidence that SARS-COV-2 constitutes a food safety risk, not considering this as a foodborne virus. Thus, the risk of contracting COVID-19 through contaminated food or through food packaging is classified as very low. So far, there are no cases of transmission through food or food packaging. The virus is primarily a respiratory virus that can also enter the bloodstream through the mucous membranes of the eyes. The existence of viruses on different surfaces, namely in food packaging, and their persistence is known for which it is recommended to follow the appropriate hygiene rules, which invariably begin with hand washing prior to handling food. These precautions must be reinforced at a professional level due to the high number of packages handled and processed foods.

The ASAE Scientific Council considers that, in view of the existing evidence, it is safe to consume food, including fruits and vegetables, valuing normal good hygiene practices in the areas of food preparation and fresh food consumption as in the non-pandemic phase.

I – Introduction / Summary of the facts

As part of the consultancy activities, the ASAE Scientific Council was asked to carry out a scientific review and update the information note “Can Coronavirus be transmitted through food?” issued by the CC, using the Thematic Panel on Risk Communication in conjunction with the Thematic Panel on Biological Risks, which was widely disseminated, through the Information Note which can be consulted at:

<https://www.asae.gov.pt/espaco-publico/destaques/pode-o-novo-tipo-de-coronavirus-ser-transmissivel-atraves-da-comida.aspx>

The Opinion aims to frame, from the point of view of scientific reasoning, an update of the information note on what is known in relation to:

- 1 Presence and possible transmission of the new SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus on surfaces and packaging
- 2 Presence of the new coronavirus in food
- 3 Ingestion and contamination through food.

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II – Analysis of the Facts

Presence and possible transmission on surfaces and food packaging

The most recent investigation, in an experimental context, points to the new coronavirus remaining up to 72 hours in plastic and stainless steel with temperatures of around 20° and humidity of 40% (1,2). Other multiple investigations have already reported that SARS-CoV-2 and other coronaviruses are able to remain on surfaces such as metal, glass, PVC, Teflon, and other materials, for several days (9-14).

Presence of the new coronavirus in food

Regarding food, the first incident occurred on June 12, 2020 at the Xinfadi agricultural products market in Beijing, where SARS-CoV-2 was detected on a cutting board used to process imported salmon (3). Although subsequent investigations have not been conclusive as to its origin, this particular incident raised, before authorities and consumers, some questions about frozen foods as possible carriers of SARS-CoV-2. Since the beginning of July 2020, at least nine food contamination incidents have been reported in China, where SARS-CoV-2 has been detected in imported foods, mainly packaging materials, from shrimp imported from Ecuador, and in Shenzhen, in Guangdong province on August 12, 2020, on the surface of frozen chicken originating in Brazil, which became the first known case in which the new coronavirus was detected in real samples of imported foods (4).

Although some studies have shown that low temperatures can dramatically prolong the persistence of SARS-CoV-2 and other coronaviruses, frozen and chilled foods have been largely neglected as potential vectors in defining risk mitigation policies and strategies.

It is described that the risk of biological contamination in general is increased by a complex agricultural production process, which may persist in the “meadow to plate” chain, which favors exposure to workers in the food sector and environmental environments. It is worth considering the possibility that the food cold chain may promote contamination, because laboratory studies (5) have shown that SARS-CoV-2 remained highly stable under refrigeration, at 4 ° C, and in freezing conditions, from - 10 to -80 ° C in fish, meat, poultry, and pig skin for 14–21 days. In a controlled laboratory study (6) the persistence of SARS-CoV-2 in chilled salmon and frozen chicken and pork for 21 days was examined. The study showed that SARS-CoV-2 titers remained virtually constant, and the inoculated viruses maintained their infectivity both in the refrigerated product (4 ° C) and in the frozen samples (-20 ° C and -80 ° C). In a previous study, conducted by the United States Army Medical Research Institute on infectious diseases, researchers presented evidence that SARS-CoV-2 can remain quite stable in pig skin for 14 days at 4 ° C (7).

Food intake and contamination

Although data on long-term survival and infectivity in these conditions are currently lacking, there is ample evidence of possible persistence of other coronaviruses, such as SARS-CoV-1. Therefore, it has been considered that contaminated food stored in refrigeration may present a risk of transmission of SARS-CoV-2 between countries and regions.

The possibility of the presence of viruses in food and refrigerated packaging is consistent with the fact that refrigeration is not considered a method of destruction but rather a preservation method.

In this context, it is up to us to summarize the evidence, risk factors, current policy and knowledge gaps about food contamination and food transmission of SARS-CoV-2.

Despite the ongoing pandemic, in many countries and regions there are no mandatory requirements for food workers to wear facial covers and gloves when handling or processing foodstuffs (8,9,10). It is

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known, however, that food handlers infected with COVID-19 can disperse droplets expelled through speech, breathing, coughing or sneezing (11,12), contaminating nearby food and its packaging.

Thus, with regard to the professional context, not only should individual protection requirements be reinforced, but cleaning recommendations, in particular from WHO, should be put in place, such as “thoroughly cleaning surfaces with water and detergent and applying disinfectants (such as alcoholic solutions to 70% or diluted sodium hypochlorite)” to destroy this type of virus. Contamination of food or food packaging can occur through handling by contaminated persons.

A completely different question is whether the presence of the virus on surfaces or in food (particularly refrigerated) constitutes a risk for the consumer. This risk can be defined in two ways: through contact with the surface of the packaging and / or food with your hands or through ingestion.

Regarding the first risk, the same procedures recommended for surface cleaning and hand washing are recommended before and after handling.

Regarding the second risk, contamination through food intake with the presence of SARS-COV-2, scientific consensus indicates that there is no evidence that SARS-COV-2 constitutes a food safety risk, and this virus is not considered to be food source. Thus, the risk of contracting COVID-19 through contaminated food or through food packaging is very low (so far, there are no cases of transmission through food or food packaging). The virus is primarily a respiratory virus that can also enter the bloodstream through the mucous membranes of the eyes. All the data that exist to date indicate that the virus cannot or cannot survive in the stomach or that the presence in food will always be in a low concentration (13).

It is in this way that the WHO and the European CDC consider that there is no evidence that COVID-19 can be contracted through food including fresh fruit and vegetables.

Also with regard to food, there are WHO recommendations for the promotion of healthy eating, which can be adopted, adding information from European Regulations, based on EFSA's scientific Opinion, for the mineral and vitamin elements that are associated with health claim “contributes to the normal functioning of the immune system” (cf. COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 432/2012 of 16 May 2012 establishing a list of permitted health claims relating to foods that do not refer to reducing the risk of disease or the development and health of children), taking into account the VRN - Nutrient Reference Value for daily intake (cf. REGULATION (EU) No 1169/2011 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 25 October 2011 on the provision of information to consumers on foodstuffs, ANNEX III - REFERENCE DOSES, PART A - DAILY REFERENCE DOSES FOR VITAMINS AND MINERALS (ADULTS)).

III – Conclusion

ASAE’s Scientific Council understands that there are knowledge gaps in the current literature on understanding the shelf life of SARS-CoV-2 in food environments under refrigeration and freezing conditions, especially on ice, a common substrate in frozen fish, meat and dairy products. These gaps should be investigated to allow informed decision making to support risk prevention policies, risk mitigation strategies, and preventive control measures regarding potential food contamination and food transmission of SARS-CoV-2.

However, there is currently no evidence that food and food packaging materials are sources or routes of transmission. Feeding animals have not so far been implicated in the transmission of COVID-19, so imported food or feed animals must undergo the same import controls as before the pandemic.

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The ASAE Scientific Council concludes that although there are knowledge gaps in the current literature on understanding the useful life of SARS-CoV-2 in food environments, it can be said that, currently, there is no evidence that people can transmit COVID-19 for food. In food, the virus that causes COVID-19 can be killed at temperatures similar to those of other known viruses and microorganisms (bacteria, fungi) found in food. Current evidence also suggests that food-producing animals are not susceptible to contracting COVID-19 and will not be infected by close contact with positive human cases.

IV – Recommendations

The ASAE Scientific Council considers that, given the existing evidence, it is safe to consume food, namely fruits and vegetables, and recommends reinforcing cleaning and protection measures in a professional environment and reinforcing cleaning and the frequency of hand washing in the domestic context reinforcing hygiene measures that were recommended before the epidemic:

- prolonged hand washing followed by appropriate drying to avoid cross-contamination (for example closing the tap with a paper towel instead of the hand that opened it while it was dirty),
- proper disinfection of work benches and tables with appropriate products
- avoid contamination between raw and cooked food
- cook and “plate” food at appropriate temperatures and wash raw food properly.
- avoid sharing food or objects between people during their preparation, cooking and consumption.

In addition to the recommendations already existing on the ASAE website, it is only proposed to add the good dietary practices that relate to the risk factors for COVID-19 identified by the scientific community (obesity, dyslipidemia, high blood pressure, cardiovascular problems), and which according to WHO are as follows:

General rule

As a general rule, the consumption of raw or undercooked animal products should be avoided. Raw meat, raw milk or raw animal organs must be handled with care to avoid cross-contamination with cooked food.

Specific rules

When cooking and preparing food, limit the amount of salt and condiments with a high sodium content (for example, soy sauce and fish sauce).

- Limit your daily salt intake to less than 5 g (approximately 1 teaspoon) and use iodized salt.
- Avoid foods (for example, snacks) that are high in salt and sugar.
- Limit your intake of soft drinks or sodas and other drinks with a high sugar content (for example, fruit juices, fruit juice concentrates and syrups, sweet flavored milks and yogurt drinks).
- Choose fresh fruits instead of savory and sweet, like cookies, cakes and chocolate.

The following can be added (in the European regulatory context):

- Eat a balanced diet according to the food wheel, ensuring the intake of food sources for the appropriate amounts (NRV) of minerals that contribute to the normal functioning of the immune system: copper, iron, folic acid, selenium, zinc, and vitamins A, B6, B12, C and D.

IV – References

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The Rapporteurs
On behalf of

The Food Risk Communication Panel
And
The Biohazard Panel

The President of the Scientific Council

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